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Future in Focus: The Centrality of Youth in Government Welfare - A Sociological Analysis

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Abstract: Government welfare policies are changing as a result of the youth population's increasing demographic significance in both developed and developing nations. The importance of adolescents in the planning, execution, and socio-political concerns of government assistance programs is examined in this essay. As society, we face the challenges of vulnerability, digital inequality, employment, and education. In addition to their demographic importance, young people are the most active forces behind social change and the advancement of the country. The government ought to acknowledge their capacity to propel social innovation, economic expansion, and demographic engagement for the advancement of the country. The present study focuses on how government take initiatives towards youth development and also availability of government programmes/policies, awareness level among youth and identify barriers and challenges faced by youth in benefiting from government welfare programmes. This sociological perspective emphasizes a paradigm shift from welfare for youth to welfare with youth. Provide suggestion which help for governance to framework policies ensuring future-oriented socio-economic development.

Keywords: Youth, Government, Welfare, Policies, Programmes

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Introduction

Young people are the most vibrant and influential group in society (the agent of social change). Young people have an increasingly important role in determining social and economic futures as countries deal with rapid globalization, technological disruption, and demographic shifts. The goals, difficulties, and agency of young people must now be the focus of government welfare, which was previously created to address poverty, health, and social security.

Sociologically speaking, this change is structural rather than just demographic, with young people being seen as both vulnerable and capable. They inspire innovation, advocacy, and cultural change while dealing with unstable employment, educational disparities, and mental health challenges. Since adolescents are now seen as active participants in development rather than passive beneficiaries of help, their significance in welfare policy reflects this paradigm shift.

In order to empower youth through inclusive education, skill development, internet access, and participatory government, this paper examines how welfare systems must change. By placing youth at the centre of welfare, governments make investments in both the short-term stability of society and its long-term viability. This paper highlights the key dimensions of Demographic, economic, social, political and technological development of youth.

Theoretical framework

Functionalist perspective

Emile Durkheim: Saw society as an integrated system where institutions (education, family, etc) maintain social order. His idea of social solidarity suggests youth welfare policies strengthen cohesion by preparing young people for productive roles.

Talcott Parsons: Developed structural functionalism and the AGIL framework (Adaptation, Goal attainment, Integration, Latency). Youth welfare fits into 'Adaptation' (training for economic productivity) and 'Integration' (socializing youth into civic life).

R.K. Merton: Proposed manifest and latent functions, Welfare schemes for youth have manifest functions like as job training, education and latent functions such as reducing unrest, fostering innovation.

Conflict perspective

Karl Marx: Highlighted class struggle. Youth often face exploitation in labour markets, with welfare acting as a buffer against capitalist inequalities.

Lewis Coser: Saw conflict as a normal and even stabilizing force. Youth protests and demands for welfare can push institutions to reform.

Ralf Dahrendorf: Emphasized authority relations. Welfare policies reflect struggles between dominant elites and marginalized youth groups.

C. Wright Mills: Link to the personal troubles to public issues. Youth unemployment or exclusion becomes a structural problem requiring welfare intervention.

Symbolic Interactionism

G H Mead: Focused on the 'self' emerging through social interaction. Welfare programs shape youth identity by signalling their value to society.

Herbert Blumer: Coined the term symbolic interactionism. Youth interpret welfare policies based on meanings constructed in everyday interactions.

C H Cooley: Proposed the looking-glass self. Youth see themselves through societal reflections, welfare schemes influence how they perceive their worth.

Erving Goffman: In his key work 'Dramaturgy' analysed social roles and presentation of self. Welfare policies affect how youth perform roles in education, work, and civic life.

Post-positivist perspective

Thomas Kuhn: The Structure of Scientific Revolutions proposed the 'paradigm shift'.

Old Paradigm: Welfare as Protection

Traditionally, welfare was designed for vulnerable groups such as the poor, elderly, or disabled. Youth were often seen as dependents, recipients of education or employment schemes, but not central actors.

Anomaly (Crisis) in the Old Paradigm

Rising youth unemployment, precarious gig work, mental health crises, and political activism challenge the adequacy of traditional welfare.

New Paradigm: Youth-Centric Welfare

- Welfare is reconceptualized as empowerment rather than mere protection
- Youth are seen as agents of social change, not passive beneficiaries
- Policies emphasis
- Skill development and entrepreneurship
- Digital inclusion
- Civic participation and leadership
- Preventive welfare (mental health, climate resilience).

Methodology

Review of Literature

Ossi Aaltonen et al. explain how administrative routines and standardized assessments in youth welfare services shape who receives support and how needs are interpreted. Their concept of "people-processing" shows that institutional procedures influence outcomes as much as policy goals, affecting

equity and access for vulnerable youth [1].

Gøsta Esping-Andersen argues that modern welfare states must shift toward social investment, especially in youth education, skill formation, and employability. He presents youth welfare as a long-term developmental strategy addressing new social risks rather than short-term assistance [2].

Walter R. Heinz discusses how globalization and labor market uncertainty complicate youth transitions from education to employment. He stresses the need for coordinated welfare, education, and employment systems to support fragmented youth life courses [3].

S. S. Kempaller highlights regional realities in Karnataka, showing how socio-cultural barriers, low awareness, and administrative inefficiencies restrict effective implementation of youth welfare schemes at the grassroots level [4].

D. R. Nagarathwar compares NCC and NSS as youth development platforms, demonstrating how participation builds leadership, discipline, and civic responsibility. His work expands the meaning of welfare to include character and capacity building [5].

J. R. Sharma emphasizes the importance of monitoring and evaluation in welfare schemes. He identifies weak accountability and lack of systematic assessment as major barriers to achieving intended outcomes for youth [6].

A. Zahruddin et al. provide a bibliometric analysis of government roles in social welfare policy, evaluation, and impact. Their study highlights the growing importance of evidence-based governance in welfare administration [7].

Émile Durkheim explains social cohesion through division of labor and functional interdependence, offering a lens to understand how welfare institutions contribute to social stability [8]. Talcott Parsons similarly views welfare institutions as mechanisms maintaining systemic order [9].

Robert K. Merton introduces manifest and latent functions, helping explain intended and unintended effects of welfare programs [10]. Karl Marx situates welfare within structural inequality and class conflict, emphasizing power relations [11].

Lewis Coser and Ralf Dahrendorf argue that social conflict can drive reform and change, relevant for understanding youth dissatisfaction and policy evolution [12], [13]. C. Wright Mills connects personal troubles of youth with broader structural issues through the sociological imagination [14].

George Herbert Mead, Herbert Blumer, Charles Horton Cooley, and Erving Goffman focus on identity, self-perception, and interaction, explaining how youth engage with welfare institutions at the micro level [15]–[18].

Thomas S. Kuhn's concept of paradigm shifts helps interpret changing approaches to youth policy and welfare governance over time [19]. The Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports, Government of India outlines current priorities for youth empowerment and participation through the National Youth Policy 2024 [20].

'Why' Importance of youth 'centrality' in welfare

Social citizenship and youth inequality:

Although welfare generally links rights to performance (education, employability, good behaviour), youth are often portrayed as the future of the country. This results in conditional citizenship, where moral assessments of "low aspirations" are incorporated into program design and aspirations are used as policy aims.

Capability approach:

Without conversion factors (placement ecosystems, employer practices), training alone perpetuates inequality rather than eliminating it. Centrality is meaningful only if programs increase real freedoms, skills that translate into jobs, access to dignified work, social recognition, and participatory voice.

Activation and conditionality: "Active" policies (skill training, entrepreneurship incentives, workfare) centre youth as agents of development but can individualize risk. When job creation lags, activation turns into surveillance and moral regulation (compliance metrics, attendance, "employability" audits).

Resource mobilization and inclusion/exclusion:

Access to networks, mentors, and information contributes to the co-production of youth

legitimacy. Those with little social capital or low digital literacy may be left out of welfare programs that rely on self-selection and digital apps.

Intersectionality: Youth outcomes differ sharply across caste, religion, gender, rural-urban location, and disability. Centrality must be assessed through these cross-cutting axe, not just age.

Aspirations as policy objects:

According to recent research, raising personal goals is viewed as a means of promoting social mobility, however this ignores the structural causes of inequality. Policies frequently focus on "mindsets" while ignoring institutional channels, which subtly perpetuates young inequity. Programs should shift from aspiration correction to institutional repair-bridge financing, anti-discrimination protections, and clear transitions from training to decent works of aspirations map onto realistic trajectories instead of motivational rhetoric, according to the implied implications.

Targeting and access

Design: Centrality falters when eligibility, documentation, or digital-only portals filter out vulnerable youth.

Delivery: Last-mile barriers (language, transport, social stigma) undercut uptake community brokers can convert intent into access.

Quality and relevance

Curriculum: Training without employer co-design yields low placement rates industry partnerships matter more than seat counts.

Dignified work: If outcomes are precarious, youth disengage; welfare must guard against funnelling youth into informal, low-wage segments.

Voice and participation

Governance: Youth councils, participatory audits, and grievance platforms shift programs from paternalism to co-production.

Measurement: Indicators should track conversion (from training to stable employment) and equity (minority youth outcomes).

Digital infrastructures

Inclusion: Mobile-first registration, vernacular interfaces, assisted enrolment, and public digital kiosks address the digital divide flagged in Karnataka contexts.

Social citizenship

Shift from compliance to capability redesign conditionalities around supports—bridge stipends, mentoring, counselling-rather than penalties.

Result and Discussion

Youth voice considers in the design and implementation of welfare scheme

One important measure of inclusion and responsiveness in government is the involvement of young people in the planning and execution of welfare programs. By including the opinions of young people, policies are certain to represent the needs, goals, and difficulties of a sizable portion of the population. Based on the responses of 330 participants, the following table shows how much young voices are taken into account in welfare plan processes.

Table 1. Table showing Youth Voice Considers in the Design and Implementation of Welfare Scheme

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Always	0	00.00
Often	0	00.00
Sometime	4	01.21
Rarely	10	03.03
Never	316	95.76

Total	330	100.00
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Above Table provides Information regarding youth voice considerations in welfare plan design and implementation is provided in the above table. No responders said that young people's opinions are frequently or always taken into account. This draws attention to a structural weakness in participatory government. Opportunities for youth input are incredibly rare, as seen by the 4 respondents (1.21%) who said that youth perspectives are occasionally taken into consideration. Ten respondents (3.03%) stated that young people's opinions are rarely taken into account, indicating tokenistic participation as opposed to meaningful engagement. A startling 316 respondents (95.76%) said that young people's opinions are never taken into account. This suggests that young people's opinions are almost completely ignored while designing and implementing social programs.

Youth as a Beneficiary or a Contributor in Welfare Scheme

Understanding whether youth are positioned as beneficiaries or contributors in welfare schemes is essential to evaluate their role in social development. The following table summarizes responses from 330 participants on this issue.

Table 2. Table showing Youth as a Beneficiary or a Contributor in Welfare Scheme

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Mainly beneficiary	323	97.87
Mainly contributor	00	00.00
Both equal	00	00.00
Neither	00	00.00
Unsure	07	02.13
Total	330	100.00

Above Table shows information about youth as a beneficiary or a contributor in welfare scheme. Overwhelming majority (97.87%) see youth as mainly beneficiaries of welfare schemes, indicating a passive role. No respondents identified youth as contributors or equal partners, highlighting a lack of participatory involvement. A small fraction (2.13%) is unsure, suggesting limited awareness or clarity about youth roles.

Biggest challenges Youth Face in Finding Employment

Employment challenges among youth are a critical concern in social and economic development. Identifying the main barriers helps policymakers and educators design effective interventions. The following table presents responses from 330 participants on the biggest challenges youth face in finding employment.

Table 3. Table showing Biggest Challenges Faced by Youth in Finding Employment

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Lack of job opportunities	37	11.21
Lack of relevant skill	283	85.76
Discrimination (age, gender, caste)	07	02.13
Poor access of job information	03	00.90
Other	00	00.00
Total	330	100.00

The table above illustrates the main obstacles young people have when trying to find work. Lack of pertinent skills was cited by the vast majority (85.76%) as the largest obstacle, highlighting the critical need for training and skill development initiatives. 11.21% of respondents mentioned a lack of employment options, which is indicative of structural problems in the labour market. Few respondents mentioned discrimination (2.13%) and inadequate access to work information (0.90%), but they nevertheless draw attention to informational and social constraints.

Government Facilities to Youth Became Job Creators

Governments play a vital role in enabling youth to transition from job seekers to job creators. By offering financial support, training, mentorship, and market access, they can foster entrepreneurship and innovation. The following table presents responses from 330 participants on how government initiatives help youth become job creators.

Table 4. Table showing Government Facilities to Youth to Became a Job Creators

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Easier access to credit/ loans	33	10.00
More training and skill-building programme	210	63.63
Stronger mentorship network	07	02.12
Simplified regulations for start-ups	00	00.00
Market linkage and global exposure	80	24.25
Total	330	100.00

The table shows government resources for young people who want to create jobs. The significance of capacity development is highlighted by the majority's (63.63%) belief that training and skill-building initiatives are the most important government assistance. Youth value opportunities beyond local bounds, as evidenced by the 24.25 percent who highlighted market linkage and worldwide exposure. Funding is still a difficulty but not the top priority, as indicated by the 10% who mentioned improved access to credit or loans. Stronger mentorship networks were indicated by just 2.12% of respondents, indicating that this field is underappreciated.

Table 5. Government Welfare Initiatives Targeting Youth

Initiative	Focus Area	Key features
National Youth Policy (2014, updated in 2024)	Empowerment and participation	targets education, skill development, employment, health, and civic engagement for India's 600 million youth under 25.
Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY)	Skill development	Provides short-term training and certification to improve employability; linked to National Skill Development Corporation.
National Programme for Youth and Adolescent Development (NPYAD)	Holistic development	Funds NGOs and institutions to run youth-centric projects in skill training, leadership, and community engagement.
Employment Linked Incentive (ELI) Scheme (2024–25 Budget)	Job creation	Incentivizes industries to generate employment opportunities tied to skill training outcomes.
Government Welfare	Technology-driven	Expands digital infrastructure and logistics,

Initiatives Targeting Youth	opportunities	aiming to create new jobs in IT and allied sectors.
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Employment Crisis Faced by Youth

High Unemployment Rates

1. Youth unemployment (ages 15-29) 10.2 per cent nationally (2023–24).
2. Urban youth unemployment, 14.7 per cent verses 8.5 per cent in rural areas. (refrr.in)

Underemployment

1. Many youths are employed in informal or low-paying jobs without social security.
2. Educated youth often take jobs below their qualification level due to lack of opportunities.

Graduate Employability Crisis

1. Only 51.25 per cent of Indian graduates are employable, reflecting a severe skills gap. (refrr.in)
2. Engineering and management graduates often lack practical skills demanded by industries.

Regional Disparities

1. States like West Bengal face youth migration due to lack of stable jobs, leading to political tensions and demands for permanent employment.

Gendered Challenges

1. Young women face higher unemployment and underemployment rates compared to men, compounded by social barriers and limited access to skill training.

Types of Unemployment Faced by Youth in Present Era

1. Educated Unemployment

Large numbers of graduates, especially in engineering, management, and social sciences, remain jobless. Only 51.25 per cent of graduates are employable, showing a mismatch between academic training and industry needs. (refrr.in)

2. Underemployment

Many youths are employed in jobs below their qualification level. Informal sector jobs dominate, offering low wages and no social security. Surveys show 36 per cent of youth (15–34 years) identify underemployment as their biggest challenge.

3. Structural Unemployment

Caused by mismatch between skills taught and jobs available. Rapid automation and digitalization reduce demand for traditional labour, while skill training programs lag behind. Youth trained under schemes like PMKVY often lack industry-relevant skills.

4. Seasonal and Rural Unemployment

Rural youth dependent on agriculture face seasonal unemployment during non-harvest periods. Migration to cities for work often results in unstable, temporary employment.

5. Disguised Unemployment

Common in rural households where more people work on farms than necessary, lowering productivity. Youth often remain in family-based work without contributing significantly to output.

6. Urban Unemployment

Urban youth unemployment rate: 18.4 per cent (July-Sept 2025), higher than rural (8-9per cent). Reflects saturation of urban job markets and limited absorption capacity of industries

Importance of the Study

Youth constitute a significant demographic segment in most societies, representing both the present workforce and the future leadership. Their inclusion in government welfare schemes is not merely a policy choice but a sociological necessity. This study emphasizes the centrality of youth in welfare programmes, analysing how their participation, access, and empowerment shape broader developmental outcomes.

Demographic Significance

Youth form a large proportion of the population in India and other developing nations. Their sheer numbers make them critical stakeholders in welfare distribution and utilization.

Understanding Youth as a Vulnerable Social Group: The study highlights youth as a structurally

vulnerable group facing unemployment, educational inequality, mental health issues, and uncertain life transitions. It helps sociologically explain these problems as outcomes of social and economic structures rather than individual failure.

Addressing Social Inequality and Stratification: This study is important for examining how class, gender, caste/ethnicity, and region shape unequal access to welfare benefits among youth. It contributes to understanding how government welfare can reduce or reproduce social inequality.

Policy Evaluation and Improvement: By focusing on youth-centered welfare, the study provides insights into the effectiveness and limitations of existing government programs. It helps policymakers design more inclusive, responsive, and sustainable youth welfare policies.

Promoting Social Stability and Integration: Youth welfare plays a crucial role in preventing social exclusion, crime, and political alienation. This study emphasizes how welfare initiatives support social integration and strengthen social cohesion.

Encouraging Intergenerational Justice: The study underlines the importance of investing in youth for long-term societal development. It stresses intergenerational equity by showing how present welfare decisions shape the future social and economic well-being of society.

Contributing to Sociological Knowledge: Academically, the study enriches sociological understanding of youth, welfare state dynamics, and social change. It links sociological theories such as functionalism, conflict theory, and life-course perspective to real-world youth issues.

Supporting Sustainable Development: Youth are key drivers of innovation and economic growth. This study demonstrates that effective welfare policies are essential for harnessing youth potential and achieving sustainable national development.

Political Participation: Youth engagement in welfare schemes fosters civic responsibility and democratic participation. It strengthens their role as agents of social change.

Justification of the Problem

Young people make up a sizable and vibrant portion of the population; they are a country's future workers, leaders, and social capital. According to sociology, young people are at a vulnerable point in their lives where long-term results are determined by their access to social mobility, work, education, and health care. Many young people are now insecure and excluded as a result of the disruption of established educational and career trajectories caused by rapid economic developments, globalization, and technology advancement. Instead of an individual failing, this leads to a structural issue.

Social stratification further intensifies the issue. Youth from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds experience limited access to quality education, healthcare, and skill development, reinforcing cycles of poverty and inequality. Without targeted welfare measures, these inequalities are reproduced across generations, threatening social justice and cohesion.

Youth welfare is also central to social stability. High levels of youth unemployment and exclusion are associated with social unrest, crime, and political alienation. From a functionalist view, welfare policies help integrate youth into society by preparing them for productive adult roles. From a conflict perspective, inadequate welfare reflects unequal power relations and neglect of marginalized youth voices.

The centrality of youth in government welfare is sociologically justified as a response to structural vulnerability, inequality, and the need for sustainable social development. Addressing youth-related problems through welfare policies is not merely supportive but preventive, ensuring social integration, intergenerational equity, and long-term national progress. Investing in youth welfare is therefore an essential strategy for securing the future of society.

Objectives

1. To examine how young are positioned as both beneficiaries and contributors within government welfare.
2. To explore issues that makes youth a critical focus on welfare.

Research Methodology and Techniques

For the present study, field survey has been carried out using scientific techniques for data collection. Qualitative and quantitative information was collected. Information was collected by the respondents with the help of mentors and experts and pre-tested and finally, the perfect questionnaire through google form

was used to gather the needed information for the present research.

Study Area and Sample

The present study focuses on postgraduate students enrolled at Kuvempu University, Shivamogga. The total population of postgraduate students is 2,180. In order to determine an appropriate sample size, Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sample size determination table was employed. Based on this scale, a representative sample of 330 students was selected. The sampling technique adopted for the study is simple random sampling, ensuring that each student in the population had an equal chance of being included. This approach enhances the reliability and generalizability of the findings to the larger postgraduate student population at Kuvempu University. Their perspectives offer valuable insights into how welfare policies are perceived, accessed, and utilized by educated youth, and how these schemes influence academic progress, career aspirations, and social inclusion. By situating the study within this university context, the research captures both the challenges and opportunities faced by young adults navigating higher education while engaging with state as well as national led welfare initiatives.

Sources of Data Collection

The present study is based on both primary and secondary sources of information. Primary data has been gathered through a field survey using a well-structured questionnaire through google from the respondents. The secondary sources of data have been gathered from published books, journal articles, periodicals, reports, theses, volumes, websites (e-sources) and others.

Data Analysis

The research methods, techniques and research data from various sources are analysed in a qualitative and quantitative manner using codification, revision, classification, indication and analysing the information in a sociological framework using adequate statistical tools.

Findings

1. 87 per cent of the respondents say that, they access education related scheme in their life it shows completely absence of skill and employment related government welfare.
2. 95 per cent of respondent response that low impact of schemes on your personal development.
3. 98 per cent of the respondents say they received financial support from government welfare thought scholarship. It shows lack of education opportunity and skill-oriented work towards the youth development.
4. 90 per cent of the student's responses say I do not contribute to the success of welfare scheme, it shows passive role of youth in implementation and design of welfare scheme.
5. 97 per cent of the respondents say youth play role as beneficiary rather than contributors in government welfare.
6. 85.76 per cent respondents says lack of job opportunities and lack of relevant skills are biggest challenge youth face in finding employment.

Suggestions

1. Government must invest in outreach campaigns to ensure youth are aware of schemes.
2. Governments prioritize education, skill development, and employment schemes to harness youth as demographic capital.
3. Government welfare programs should shift from a general population approach to a youth-centered framework, recognizing young people as active social agents rather than passive beneficiaries.
4. Welfare schemes should integrate education, skill development, and employment pathways.
5. Promote Inclusive Welfare for Marginalized Youth. Inclusive welfare helps reduce social inequality and supports social mobility.
6. Encourage Youth should be actively involved in the design, implementation, and evaluation of welfare programs.
7. Future welfare policies must recognize mental health, substance abuse, and social alienation as critical youth issues.
8. Leverage digital platforms for welfare delivery because digitalization can improve access, transparency, and efficiency of welfare schemes.

9. Youth welfare policies should adopt a gender-sensitive approach, addressing issues like female education, employment discrimination, early marriage, and safety.
10. Welfare initiatives should encourage civic participation, volunteerism, and leadership training among youth. These fosters social responsibility and strengthens social cohesion.
11. Use research, surveys, and youth data should guide welfare evidence-based policies which ensure efficient resource allocation and measurable social outcomes.
12. Future government welfare must focus on empowerment rather than dependency, emphasizing capacity-building, entrepreneurship, and sustainable livelihoods.

Conclusion

The centrality of youth in government welfare is not only a demographic imperative but also a sociological necessity. Youth represent the most dynamic segment of society, embodying both vulnerability and potential. Welfare schemes directed toward them serve as instruments of empowerment, bridging structural inequalities and enabling social mobility. From the lens of sociological theory, these interventions highlight the role of the state in resource mobilization, social inclusion, and functional integration of diverse communities. The effectiveness of youth-centered welfare depends on accessibility, awareness, and inclusivity. Marginalized groups such as rural youth, minorities, and those in precarious professions often remain excluded from the full benefits of welfare programs. Addressing these gaps is essential for ensuring that welfare does not merely function as a safety net but as a transformative tool for equity and justice. In the end, putting young people at the centre of welfare policy shows a dedication to democratic vibrancy and sustainable growth. Governments may turn young people from passive beneficiaries into active social change agents by making investments in education, health, skill development, and participatory governance. Therefore, acknowledging young people as both beneficiaries and co-creators of inclusive and resilient societies is essential to the future of welfare.

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